

Komeda: Framework for Interactive Algorithmic Music On Embedded Systems

Krystian Baclawski

Institute of Computer Science
University of Wrocław

krystian.baclawski@ii.uni.wroc.pl

Dariusz Jackowski

Institute of Computer Science
University of Wrocław

dariusz.jackowski@ii.uni.wroc.pl

ABSTRACT

Application of embedded systems to music installations is limited due to the absence of convenient software development tools. This is a very unfortunate situation as these systems offer an array of advantages over desktop or laptop computers. Small size of embedded systems is a factor that makes them especially suitable for incorporation into various forms of art. These devices are effortlessly expandable with various sensors and can produce rich audio-visual effects. Their low price makes it affordable to build and experiment with networks of cooperating devices that generate music.

In this paper we describe the design of Komeda – implementation platform for interactive algorithmic music tailored for embedded systems. Our framework consists of music description language, intermediate binary representation and portable virtual machine with user defined extensions (called modules).

1. INTRODUCTION

We believe that artists creating music installations are limited by the choice of platforms that can run their software. Personal computers, either desktops or laptops, can be too obstructive to the visual and spatial form of an installation. Mobile devices (i.e. phones and tablets) are not well suited for this purpose – problems like: device cost, replaceability, complex software stack, limited battery life, difficulties with expandability (i.e. no easy way to add custom external sensors and output devices) don't make them a great choice. Apparently the most viable option is to use small embedded systems, which could be easily incorporated into both static and movable parts of a music installation. Such systems should be build with affordable components and be easily expandable with peripherals. It is natural step forward to construct systems composed of handful or tens of such devices. An artist that desires to explore the idea of distributed music generation should be able to easily expand the system with communication capabilities and protocols. Hardware that matches the description above already exists, but it's not backed up by

solid software framework that enables easy creation of musical applications.

Such platform should include:

- music notation language,
- hardware independent binary representation,
- portable virtual machine capable of playing music,
- communication protocol (also wireless),
- interface for sensors and output devices,
- support for music generation routines.

We would like to present the Komeda system, which currently provides only a subset of the features listed above, but in the future should encompass all of them.

2. OVERVIEW

Komeda consists of the following components: music description language, intermediate binary representation, virtual machine and module system. The language helps to create a musical score with place holders – so called "blanks" – which are filled in by the code running as a part of user defined module. The score takes a form of note sequence organized into patterns. In addition to that the language offers a limited set of control structures, pattern invocation and statements that allow communication with modules. Modules may represent instruments, note generator algorithms, sensors, etc. Each module is assigned a set of parameters and actions that a user can read, modify or invoke, respectively. The binary representation was designed to be platform independent bytecode for KomedaVM. The virtual machine provides player routine – or more specifically a scheduler and driver for instrument modules – and an interpreter for the bytecode.

3. LANGUAGE

3.1 Design

The first and the most important component of Komeda platform – at least from user's point of view – is the language. It is mainly focused on providing a succinct music notation description. However, it is not solely a data definition language like XML. It incorporates computation statements, control structures and other features specific to programming languages. We enable the user to express easily following concepts:

- music organized into parts (i.e. patterns, phrases, choruses),

- rich structure of music score (incl. loops, repetitions, alternatives),
- playback of score fragment in modified context (i.e. transposition, volume change),
- virtual player synchronisation (e.g. concerted transition to next music part),
- interaction with external world (e.g. sensors, controllers).

Having language users without much of a former experience, we would like them to find the concepts clear and the code readable. To help with adoption of Komeda, we decided to base its syntax on something widely known in both worlds – of music notation and programming languages. Hence, significant number of concepts were borrowed from LilyPond [1] and Java.

The main challenges we experienced while designing Komeda were:

- capturing all concepts needed to represent music score unambiguously – i.e. a user should be encouraged to express ideas in the least number of possible ways,
- balancing between having a readable syntax and concise notation – note that these two aspects collide with each other, as shorter constructs become more obscure,
- finding effective mapping to intermediate form (Komeda bytecode) – shape of binary data that represents the music to be executed in VM,
- simplicity of virtual machine and user modules.

Our design went a complete overhaul several times, as we were discovering dependencies between all three layers of Komeda environment: the language, the binary representation and the virtual machine.

At the time of writing we have working compiler from Komeda to intermediate representation. The implementation is written in Haskell, a purely functional language with strong static typing. Our choice is justified by a few arguments:

- Haskell [2] has set of rich abstractions and expressive types - our code looks clear and simple, there is little verbosity or boilerplate code, that obliterates the ideas,
- availability of great parser frameworks – Parsec [3] is used to express Komeda grammar.

3.2 Theoretical considerations

We choose to model the language after western music notation (with Helmholtz pitch notation). It has many drawbacks, nonetheless it is the most popular music notation which virtually anyone can read. Every person having former experience with western music notation should immediately recognize familiar structures in Komeda language. On the other hand we didn't try to create a music engraving language, so we had some flexibility in implementing musical concepts. In some cases we completely resign from

some of them – most notable examples are key signatures, bars and time signatures. Here we would like to supply couple of arguments for these omissions.

The notion of key signature associated with tonality was made somewhat obsolete by atonal techniques or scales other than modes of the major system. Moreover, introducing the key signature could result in the decreased readability. Such is the case with Oliver Messaien's prelude *La colombe* notated in E major key in which most of the chords have more than one accidental, which makes hard to keep track of exact pitches in signatures with four sharps. Similarly notation of music based on the non-standard heptatonic scales requires custom key signatures (e.g. some of the pieces from Bela Bartok's *Microcosmos* which utilize both flats and sharps in the signature) or usage of accidentals instead of the key signature. Scales with more than seven pitch class appearing for example in the music of Bartok [4] [5] and Messaien (whose modes of limited transposition [6] mostly have more than seven tones) cannot be notated without accidentals. The same happens with works based on the serialism, dodecaphony and intervals pairings [7] or other atonal techniques. There is also another argument for foregoing the key signature even for tonal works. Contemporary composers often chose to notate them with only accidentals - great example here is the first movement of III Symphony by Henryk Górecki, who always notated F# with accidental in this E-minor piece.

Bars and metre are used in music mainly for three things: structuring, as a help for the performer in keeping track of the score and to introduce default accents in music. In Komeda the visual structure of music can be imposed using the white characters and comments. Obviously Komeda does not need any help in keeping track of the score, so we are left with only last application of measures. The problem of accent induced by metre is that there is not one standard of it. Underlying pulse of different time signatures is associated with genre, period and personal styles of both the composer and the performer. Moreover in the contemporary music the implicit accent is non-existent [8]. The lack of bars also simplify music generation.

3.3 Syntax concepts

3.3.1 Channels

Top-level construct of komeda language is a channel. It describes a behavior of monophonic audio source. Each channel is assigned an independent thread of execution that interprets Komeda language and in turn produces note sequence to be played.

```
channel 0 play @Pattern0
```

Listing 1: Channel notation example

The definition above states, that the channel number 0 will play a program defined by `Pattern0`. Number of channels is limited by the implementation of KomedaVM and may depend on hardware capabilities.

Note that the program executed by the channel may make use of certain sensor, voices or generator modules. That information has to be specified in channel initialization rou-

tine that is automatically added by the compiler. Thus code analysis has to be performed at compile time.

3.3.2 Identifiers and Parameters

Komeda programs will assign names to specific objects like patterns, voices, etc. Another group of names refer to certain playback parameters like tempo, volume, etc. Hence two groups of identifiers were conceived to capture these concepts. All user introduced identifiers begin with "@" sign, followed by uppercase letter (e.g. @FooBar). Parameters follow similar syntax, though they begin with lowercase letter (e.g. @tempo). Some of them are built into language (i.e. channel control), but others depend on modules imported into the scope of a channel.

3.3.3 Patterns

They are used to give music score a basic structure. Each pattern is given a unique name and can be referred to from other patterns, as if it was copied into the place of reference. Pattern execution interprets notes and control commands hold within its structure.

```
pattern @Pattern0 {
  ...
  @Pattern1
  ...
}

pattern @Pattern1 {
  ...
}
```

Listing 2: Example of pattern invocation

3.3.4 Notes, Rests and Slurs

Fundamental concept embraced by Komeda is a note. It is specified by pitch (semitone) and note length. Closely related to a note is a rest, which stops playback for a given unit of time. The timing is implicit – i.e. notes starts when a previous one stops. Pitch is expressed in Helmholtz notation with sharps only – we decided to drop flats. Length is represented as a fraction of default time unit, which allowed us to omit a concept of tuples (e.g. triplet) and dots from standard notation. The tempo is always expressed in quarter notes per minute.

```
@tempo 120
@unit 1/4

C#, D r a3/2 d' /2 e2
```

Listing 3: Sample music score

Komeda supports expressing slurs and ties as well, though they are immediately coalesced into a single note at compilation time.

```
a~a/2 c~d~e2~f
```

Listing 4: Expressing slurs

3.3.5 Control Structures

Usually a score consist of a few fragments that are repeated several times. Certainly one would like to express that concisely, possibly giving alternative endings – western music notation uses volta brackets for that purpose. Komeda is more flexible as it allows to designate alternative fragments (not only endings) on specified loop iteration. Note that alternative fragments don't have to be defined for each iteration, which can lead to repetitions of different lengths. It's also possible to nest repetitions as shown below:

```
times 8 {
  ...
  on 3 {
    ...
    times 2 {
      /* do it twice on 3rd repetition
        of outer loop */
      ...
    }
  }
  ...
  on 4 { ... }
}
```

Listing 5: Nested loops and alternatives

However sometimes one would like to express possibly infinite repetition that can be terminated under certain condition (e.g. user interaction). That is achievable using forever construct.

```
forever {
  ...
  if @Button.pressed()
    break
  ...
}
```

Listing 6: Infinite loop with break on user action

3.3.6 Context Changes

There are several cases, when a user would like to perform series of similar actions, captured by a pattern, but with slightly different settings. Example of such situation is when a user wants to play a pattern representing some phrase with a transposition.

```
with @pitch +3 @volume +10% {
  @NoteSequence
}

with @pitch -2 {
  @NoteSequence
}
```

Listing 7: Temporary parameters modification

The with statement can be used to temporarily change a set of parameters for the commands placed in its scope.

3.3.7 Synchronisation

Channels are inherently independent. Hence, instructions interpreted within a channel have no way to obtain information about state of another channel. While this isola-

tion is generally a good idea, it poses a problem when timing between channels is required to achieve desired effect (e.g. smooth transition from one music part to another). To synchronize players, we introduced simple, but effective mechanisms based on the idea of notifications and rendezvous points.

In example below we devise a meeting point for two players. They will only advance to the next part of music, when they both arrive at @Part2.

```
rendezvous @Part2 for 2

pattern @PatA {
  times 3 { ... }
  ...
  arrive @Part2
  ...
}

pattern @PatB {
  ...
  times 2 { ... }
  arrive @Part2
  ...
}
```

Listing 8: Use of meeting points for synchronization

Another example requiring synchronization is two players, who improvise at the beginning and afterwards want to transition to main theme of work.

```
signal @StopImprovisation

pattern @PatC {
  ...
  /* to drummer: stop improvisation! */
  notify @StopImprovisation
  ...
}

pattern @PatD {
  ...
  until @StopImprovisation {
    // some crazy beats :)
  }
  ...
}
```

Listing 9: Communication through signalling

3.3.8 Instruments

Currently only simple DDS [9] instruments are supported for simplicity's sake. Simple DDS instrument is generated by a single oscillator (e.g. "sine", "triangle", "square", "noise") and ADSR¹ envelope. Such instruments can be supported on even the simplest hardware and are a good starting point for generation of more advanced sounds.

```
voice @SomeWave = @SimpleDDS {
  @osc "sine"
  @adsr 0.1 0.1 0.8 0.9
}
```

Listing 10: Example voice definition

In the example above a new instrument is created by calling constructor of imported *SimpleDDS* module.

¹ Attack-Decay-Sustain-Release

4. VIRTUAL MACHINE

KomedaVM is a small piece of software residing in flash memory of an embedded device. It is responsible for loading (from flash, RAM or if applicable some external sources such as SD cards) binary representation of Komeda language and executing it. For this purpose the machine has to maintain a global state and for each channel a private state. Additionally, it manages modules currently in use and schedule execution of instruments playback. Certain assumptions described in this chapter influenced shape of the language or imposed particular constraints on the design (e.g. number of available channels).

4.1 Binary representation

Almost all Komeda language concepts have their counterparts in binary representation. Some of composite high-level instructions are split down into simpler constructs as the compiler lowers the code. At the very bottom each channel behaves as an independent state machine – a very simple microprocessor with specialized set of instructions. We will not provide details of instruction set architecture (ISA) employed by KomedaVM, as it is still undergoing significant changes.

Having spent considerable amount of time analyzing contemporary micro-controllers ISAs, we decided to keep close to these designs. Affinities we would like to preserve are:

Reduced number of orthogonal instructions. If we keep virtual instruction design close enough to existing ISA, for instance AVR [10], we possibly could provide one-to-one mapping between Komeda and native instructions. That could reduce the size of interpreter as the processor is able to execute some instructions directly. While it is tempting to follow such path, certainly specialization hinders portability of virtual machine, which at the moment is our priority goal. Thus, we decided to take opposite approach, and deliver instructions that can be interpreted easily on most popular embedded processors, which tend to have RISC-like ISAs [11].

Sizeable register file and a stack. Komeda language is mainly oriented towards expressing control flow – it is not suitable for data processing. Thus, we decided to drop concept of program's memory, which anyway is a scarce resource in embedded systems. Instead, we use virtual registers and stack to store state of the program. The requirement for virtual stack emerged as we considered situation, when a pattern invokes another pattern – in some sense it mimics concept of function calls and activation records from general purpose programming languages.

Uniform size of instructions i.e. 2 bytes. If Komeda binary representation is going to be interpreted in software, the interpreter must be able to quickly decode and dispatch instructions. Such representation is also convenient, if we allow any arbitrary Komeda code processing (e.g. compilation or whole pattern generation by native code).

4.2 Modules

From the virtual machine point of view, modules are independent entities. The communications with them is performed via specialized structure, which has to be initialized by KomedaVM before execution of a program. The machine is allowed to call a specific action assigned to a module. This is the only conceivable moment in which we allow the control to be transferred out of KomedaVM to native code.

Lets consider a single module. Firstly, we would like to avoid exposing the state of a module to the virtual machine, if possible. Secondly, when you consider module's internal state, it may be too large to be represented by the interface visible to KomedaVM – i.e. virtual registers. Thus the machine has to maintain the state that is not visible to Komeda code directly. Each module may be subjected to non-trivial initialization. Finally, a program may use same module but differently initialized or used in two different independent contexts.

As a consequence, we decided to design modules in spirit of object oriented paradigm, but without inheritance for now. Lots of similarities emerged – clearly modules are classes, modules with attached state are class instantiations (i.e. objects), parameters are public properties of an object, and remote procedures – just methods. Such model can be efficiently mapped onto C language which lacks of object oriented features.

4.3 Execution engine

Runtime system is composed of three components characterized shortly below.

NotePlayer Central subsystem of Komeda runtime. It is a scheduler that takes care of updating the state of channels (i.e. note pitch and length, slur mode, instrument number) and reprogramming AudioPlayer respectively. For each note being played NotePlayer maintains an alarm clock, which is triggered when the note is about to stop being played. Next note is then fetched and AudioPlayer reprogrammed to play it. Secondary functionality is related to the maintenance of synchronization state between channels.

AudioPlayer Its main task is to continuously generate and mix all audio inputs into a stream suitable to be digested by audio playback device. This subsystem is considered to be the most platform dependant constituent. Playback device implementation may vary greatly for each hardware platform. It can be implemented as a DAC with or without DMA (i.e. DAC capable of feeding itself with consecutive samples without involving processor), a simple PWM generator, FM synthesis sound chip, etc. AudioPlayer may be programmed to perform certain non-trivial computation like direct digital sound synthesis, or system interaction like fetching samples from storage device. It seems to be the only subsystem that needs to be called synchronously by the system clock.

Interpreter Subsystem invoked by NotePlayer to update the state of a channel. Each interpreter invocation has to

end up producing a note information or a rest, eventually forcing interpreter to enter wait state on that channel. The result is obtained by executing compiled Komeda language statements.

NoteGenerator An optional subsystem written in C language that either was assigned to a channel by a programmer or temporarily suppressed Komeda interpreter and intercepted its execution. It employs certain algorithm to deliver notes or rests upon channel update action.

5. FUTURE WORK

5.1 Features currently in development

At the time of writing Komeda is under active development. That means some of its interesting features undergo implementation process and are being evaluated with regards to language and virtual machine design. Our long term focus is the support for embedded platforms, such as Arduino [12], 8-bit and 16-bit microcontrollers (PIC, DSPIC, AVR, etc.) with built-in or attached digital-to-analog converters.

One of currently identified design issues is platform specific instruments support. For many embedded devices, especially those without D/A converter, implementation of DDS-based instruments is either cumbersome or utterly impractical (overhead of using PWM for DDS is too high). On the other hand, those devices are likely to have some native support for generation of simple waves, e.g. PWM-based square wave generator. Other conceivable platform specific instruments are external devices controlled via MIDI interface or mechanical devices that control real instruments. Whole range of possibilities is available here – from simple sine wave generator, through MIDI synthesizers, to another embedded device controlling servo arm playing xylophone.

Extending Komeda with flexible DDS instruments is not trivial and requires careful review of module system. Direct digital synthesis can consume virtually all computing resources and may affect note scheduling, which we want to avoid at all cost.

Interface delivered by modules should be flexible enough to extended the system beyond proposed purposes. Two more types of pluggable modules, other than instruments, are envisioned: sensors and generators.

- Sensors purpose is to measure physical quantities such as light intensity, magnetic field direction, temperature, etc.; and interpret them in a context of music. The values coming from sensors could be used to play a note, set new tempo rate or voice volume — i.e. control virtually any other music parameter available. Example mapping could translate room temperature into music tempo (i.e. hotter or cooler into faster or slower respectively) or light intensity into base pitch of notes being played (i.e. lighter or darker into higher or lower respectively).
- Generators are additional mechanism for employing generative music techniques. Their role is to deliver a number of values upon request – a user has

freedom to use these values as she wishes. Alternatively the channel could be forced to execute code generated by the module until the generator returns control. At the moment of writing music generation can only be achieved by external code modifying Komeda pattern binary representation. While this method is the most powerful one, almost certainly is the most difficult to use properly.

5.2 Planned features

Arguably the most needed feature of Komeda is language supported rich sound synthesis – instead of just simple DDS instruments implemented as external modules. There are a few issues worth mentioning:

- There is a need to extend the language to easily supply required synthesis arguments in a concise way.
- In chosen model the notes are the only acoustic events. They are mutually independent, save slurs, and take parameters only at initialization time. Though suitable for representing musical score this approach is somewhat limited. Especially when it comes to representing sounds with continuously changing spectra or indefinite pitch, etc.
- Last but not least, if Komeda was to support synthesis techniques, it would be necessary to extend the language with instrument specification. There are two possibilities to incorporate this into the main language. First option is to extend voice definitions with a new language for instrument specification. Such language could be modelled after CSound orchestra [13] or Nyquist .alg [14] files. Second option is to extend Komeda language with extra constructs expressing additional sonic events inside patterns. The later approach would greatly increase the expressive power of the language, but could lead to performance loss and increased complexity of the system.

Another important deficiency of Komeda is absence of continuous parameter control. That makes it impossible to express portamento and similar effect. Create ritardando or accelerando and crescendo or decrescendo is very problematic, as it needs assignment of different tempo or volume to each consecutive note. We find three possibilities to solve that – to allow only linear function, piecewise linear (i.e. envelopes) or arbitrary functions implemented as arrays.

For implementation of some non essential features we could add source code macros. Examples are: symbolic description of tempo or volume levels, flats, mordents and other ornaments. In addition, given enough expressive power, the macros could be used to create tools for generating or transforming score according to some compositional system. We are considering both text-substitution and compile time macros.

To increase expressive power we could introduce microtones and tunings other than equal temperament. The later is easier, as we represent pitch by discrete number.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Komeda is a complex system and describing its intricacies goes way beyond the scope of this paper. Instead we decided to present its philosophy and design decisions. We also chose to list ideas encountered during development stages. We hope that people creating similar platforms will find these information useful.

As for the future of Komeda, we hope to release a first public version in the next few months. As more and more planned features are being incorporated, the platform calls for a full evaluation in the form of an installation or a novel instrument. We are going to choose several artists for co-operation. Moreover, we would like to reiterate some concepts from the Komeda, to provide an even more flexible and easy to use platform.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] [Online]. Available: <http://www.lilypond.org/>
- [2] [Online]. Available: <http://www.haskell.org/>
- [3] [Online]. Available: <http://www.haskell.org/haskellwiki/Parsec>
- [4] E. Antokoletz, *The Music of Bela Bartok: A Study of Tonality and Progression in Twentieth-Century Music*. University of California Press, 1990.
- [5] E. Lendva, *Bela Bartok: An Analysis of His Music*. Pro Am Music Resources, 1991.
- [6] O. Messiaen, *Technique de mon langage musical*. Alphonse Leduc, 1944.
- [7] J. C. B. Rae, *Pitch organisation in the music of Witold Lutoslawski since 1979*. PhD thesis, University of Leeds, 1992.
- [8] V. Persichetti, *Twentieth-Century Harmony: Creative Aspects and Practice*. W. W. Norton & Company, 1961.
- [9] T. Holmes, *Electronic and Experimental Music: Technology, Music, and Culture*. Routledge, 2008.
- [10] [Online]. Available: <http://www.atmel.com/products/microcontrollers/avr/default.aspx>
- [11] [Online]. Available: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reduced_instruction_set_computer
- [12] [Online]. Available: <http://www.arduino.cc>
- [13] [Online]. Available: <http://www.csounds.com/manual/html/OrchTop.html>
- [14] [Online]. Available: <http://www.cs.cmu.edu/~rbd/doc/nyquist/part16.html>